

Sahyadri Khanda (Purana)

also known as “Sthala-Purana (regional Purana text)”

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Entry tags: Vaishnavism, South Asian Religion, Shaivism, Purana, Hindu Narrative text, Religious Group, Text

Part of a regional textual tradition in late-medieval western India (c. 1400 - 1800 CE). The text of Sahyadri Khanda self-proclaims to be a part of Skanda Purana and quotes from other main Puranas to build a narrative for the cultural landscape of western coast of India. A part of Hindu narrative tradition, the text establishes itself as both Vaishnava and Shiva traditional text in western India. The text is popular amongst the population in modern Maharashtra, Karnataka and Kerala.

Date Range: 1400 CE - 1800 CE

Region: Western Coast of India

Region tags: India, Western India, Western Coast of India, Maharashtra, Kerala, Karnataka

The text narrativizes the geography along the west coast of India, roughly spanning from the south of Raigad district in Maharashtra to the north of Kozhikode in Kerala. The narratives are often dotted and give descriptions of one region more than the other while pushing for a common sacred origin for the entire west coast of India.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Levitt, Stephan Hillyer. 1977. "The Sahyadrikhanda: Some Problems Concerning a Text-Critical Edition of a Puranic-text". Purana, 19.1

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://journal.fi/store/article/view/65156>

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/Sahyadri-Khanda>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Notes: Manuscripts housed at Saraswati Mahal (Karnataka, India), Benaras (Uttar Pradesh, India) and a photocopies of now lost manuscript at LD Institute, Ahmedabad and Oriental Institute, Vadodara (Gujarat, India)

– Printed with moveable type

Notes: The extant version of Sahyadri Khanda edited by Garson da Cunha in 1877 CE is widely available and read in select congregations, temple meetings and religious discourse in villages along the west coast of India. (Inclusion of narratives from Sahyadri Khanda in public discourse in towns of Guhagar, Kaseli, Malvan, and Vengurla (Maharashtra) are recorded in 2017-2019.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: unknown

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Overwritten

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: Numerous manuscripts of the text housed at various locations in India. Cochin manuscript (90 chapters), Junnar (100 chapters), six manuscripts from Mumbai (then Bombay) in Maharashtra state. Three manuscripts from Kota, Sidhapura, and Chempi in Karnataka state. A manuscript from Goa dated to 1700 CE. A manuscript from Benares containing 100 chapters.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– I don't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: This is a rather grey area for the textual authority of Sahyadri-Khanda. Some of the sociological prescriptions/descriptions in the text are taken to be "official" in some cases. However, the text does not implicitly push for religious authority.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: Sanskrit

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Yes

Notes: Stephen Levitt suggests interpolation and demonstrates certain sections in the text as a product of Sanskrit used in different regions. Instances of creolization or blended language is apparent in other texts associated with the text (such as Renuka Mahatmya, Mangesh-akhyan, Chandrachudamahatmya, etc)

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Other [specify]: Local devotees and self-identified Hindu people and Brahmins.

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– I don't know

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Performative traditions, local theatre performances, and ritually mediated social spheres are some of the areas that support a religious study of the text in Konkan. (Attached photos show local theatre performances based on the narratives from Sahyadri Khanda as an offering to the village deity. The local theatre performance "Dashavatari" emerged from a long-standing tradition of performing select narratives from the Puranas and Sthala Mahatmyas as a ritual offering to the deity. The performance in the temple of the village deity generally inaugurates a season-long series of ritual performances for the deities.)

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Yes

↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

– I don't know

Notes: Regionally accepted versions are popular in particular towns/groups

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– I don't know

Notes: There are various hypotheses regarding the extant version of Sahyadri Khanda. Since Sahyadri Khanda can be considered as an open canon, and numerous local mahatmya texts (eulogical texts) have adopted from and contributed to the corpus of Sahyadri Khanda, one can assume this text to be a part of a collection of texts. Sahyadri Khanda is described as being a part of Skanda Purana.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: A commentary on the "varna" and "jati", along with the practices allowed and taboo for certain groups are prescribed in the text.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Additionally, the text attempts to trace a sociological history of the region

along the west coast of India.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: Outlines social hierarchies and prescribes "varna-proper" duties

– Vocabulary

Notes: Introduces the readers to overarching themes and vocabulary in Hinduism. Some details such as units of measurement (kos, yojana, etc), sacrifices such as Agnihotra, and practices such as kshepan (haircutting), are introduced in the text.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– Yes

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Supernatural forces

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Solar?

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

- ↳ Planting?
 - No

- ↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)
 - No

- ↳ Harvest?
 - No

- ↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?
 - No

- ↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)
 - Yes

- ↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?
 - No

- ↳ Marriage?
 - Yes

- ↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?
 - No

- ↳ Divorce?
 - No

- ↳ Warfare?
 - No

- ↳ Funerary services?
 - Yes

- ↳ Trade/commerce?
 - Yes

↳ Festivals?

– No

Notes: Some festivals are mentioned by names, without any further specifications. The text identifies some sites associated with specific rites, but not festivals as such.

↳ Pilgrimages?

– No

↳ Feasting?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– I don't know

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

↳ In human form?

– No

Notes: Depends on the individual case in the narrative

↳ In animal/plant form?

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– Yes

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– I don't know

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– I don't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

Notes: Most of the funerary associations in the text are associated with sites in proximity of Shiva temple

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: A group of high-gods, with supernatural beings such as yaksha, kinnara, etc

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– I don't know

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The reflexivity between the presence of supernatural beings on the local landscape as a result of textual narratives is difficult to attest. The physical representation of the presence of temples and shrines along the west coast of India could be in part a result of the textual tradition.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?
 - Yes

Does the text guide divination practices?

- No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

- No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

- No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

- No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

- Yes

- ↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
 - Yes

- ↳ Alive, identified
 - Yes

Notes: The text assumes the foreknowledge about Parashurama's nature of existence as being an immortal. Although the text of Sahyadri Khanda does not use the word "chiranjivi", the narrative is self-aware of Parashurama's eternal existence and various episodes recounted in the text assume his existence through time.

- ↳ Coming in this lifetime
 - No

- ↳ Coming on a specified date
 - No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ Coming has already passed

– Yes

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs

– Yes

Notes: although the "avatar" theory deviates from the concept of messiahs, the narratives can be interpreted with Parashurama as the savior or messiah for the Brahmin groups described in the text.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

Notes: Parashurama is born to a Brahmin father and Kshatriya mother. Parashurama creates a landmass and invites Brahmins to reside and hold land ownership. In some ways, Parashurama in the text of Sahyadri Khanda pushes for a re-attuning of religious and political systems. Although this suggestion is latent in the text, cultural literacy around the implications of the Parashurama narrative is assumed by the writers of the text.

↳ Other purpose

–Specify: General consensus on Parashurama's life-purpose is to oust the tyrannical Kshatriya rulers.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Yes

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– Yes

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The time of eschaton took place in the past, as recorded in the text

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Yes

↳ Establishment of new political system

– Yes

Notes: Although the text does not overtly propose a new political system, the narrative suggests overthrowing the then existing political rulers (Kshatriyas) and the land donated to Brahmins - for governance?

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– I don't know

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– Yes

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– Yes

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– Yes

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals within society (Excepting slaves, aliens)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Courage (in battle)
 - No
- ↳ Courage (generic)
 - No
- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
 - No
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - No
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - Yes

- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - Yes
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - Yes
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - No
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– I don't know

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

Notes: In a limited sense; orderliness and cleanliness associated with the purity of "varna" hinted at, in the text.

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Filial piety, performing caste/class-specific roles, etc.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Yes

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

↳ Circumcision?

– No

↳ Food taboos?

– Yes

↳ Hair?

– No

↳ Dress?

– No

↳ Ornaments?

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

↳ Other?

– Specify: Belonging to a certain social group

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– I don't know

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– Yes

↳ Comedy?

– No

↳ Tragedy?

– Yes

↳ Epic entertainment?

– Yes

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

- ↳ Are they mandatory?
 - No
 - Notes: Specific to certain social groups
- ↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Offering of land is important, especially from rulers/kings to the Brahmins
- ↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?
 - No
- ↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?
 - No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

- A chiefdom

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A chiefdom

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Some rulers (namely Bajiaro I, the Peshwa during Maratha rule in c. 1700-1740) and some groups of Brahmins have been involved in the systematic erasure of the content from the text. The present text stands as a collection of extant fragments from manuscripts.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Notes: No mention of institutionalized welfare efforts - except Brahmins arriving in the region of Konkan on invitation by the local rulers. The text mentions donation of land to Brahmins, which could be interpreted as welfare efforts towards a particular social group.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Yes

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The form of warfare mentioned in the text takes the form of "divine warfare". As Brian Collins mentions in the book "The Other Rama...", the intention of the warfare implies eradication of a specific social class, the Kshatriyas, at the hands of a Brahmin. The text delves in bloody descriptions of the warfare to side with the Brahmin group in presenting the narrative so as to position the Brahmins as heroes.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: cursory indication of local food production when local flora and offerings to the deities come into the discussion. However, no special attention to food production or institutionalized efforts.

Bibliography

General References

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